

PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF GENDER CULTURE OF THE MODERN ENLIGHTENERS

Ochilova Gulnoza Asrorovna

Shahrisabz State Pedagogical Institute

Teacher of the Department of Pedagogy

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19327471>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 24th March 2026

Accepted: 26th March 2026

Online: 28th March 2026

KEYWORDS

gender equality, family strength, politics, economy, law, ideology and culture, education, science, oriental gender equality

ABSTRACT

This article contains opinions about the reforms and changes carried out by the state regarding the development of gender culture today. Also, the pedagogical views of western and eastern scholars and modern enlighteners on the formation of gender culture were discussed.

There are many scientific views on the development of gender culture, which is one of the important problems today. The reason for this is that the correct formation of gender relations is important for the development of society. Therefore, in his speech at the 46th session of the United Nations Human Rights Council, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, stated: "We will firmly continue the work aimed at radically increasing the role of women in the socio-political life of our country and in the field of business in relation to gender policy issues." It is known that in accordance with the resolution No. 70 of the United Nations General Assembly adopted at the Summit on Sustainable Development held in September 2015, as well as in order to organize systematic work on the consistent implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations Global Agenda in the period up to 2030, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "Up to 2030 adopted a decision on measures to implement national goals and objectives in the field of sustainable development. At the same time, within the framework of the implementation of the Fifth Sustainable Development Goal, Uzbekistan has developed nine tasks related to "Ensuring gender equality and expanding the rights and opportunities of all women". In accordance with the tasks of the fifth goal (Gender equality), by 2030 it is necessary to eliminate all forms of discrimination against all women, to ensure the full and effective participation of women at all levels of decision-making in political, economic and social life, and equal opportunities for leadership.

In addition, this goal includes the implementation of gender equality principles in the process of adoption of State programs at different levels of the state. In recent years, efforts to ensure gender equality and increase the role of women in social and political life have been carried out in several directions:

improvement of legislation on women's rights;

improvement of the institutional foundations of women's protection;
raising awareness of the population about gender equality and women's rights;
training of responsible officials based on relevant legal norms to ensure their compliance in law enforcement practice.

Article 46 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "Men and women have equal rights". Therefore, the international, legal and constitutional legal basis of gender equality is guaranteed. Gender equality also means social equality.

Gender is a social condition of relations between men and women in all spheres of social life and activities, including politics, economy, law, ideology and culture, education, and science. The word "gender" is derived from the English word "gender" and the Latin word "genus" and means "breed, sex, origin". If biological sex divides people into women and men, then gender is aimed at separating the place of women and men in society.

In order for women and men to find and determine their place in society, the state creates the same conditions and opportunities for them, which serves as the basis for ensuring gender equality. In recent years, important measures have been taken to strengthen the legal and institutional basis of ensuring gender equality in Uzbekistan. Issues of gender equality are also reflected in our national legislation, that is, on September 2, 2019, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men" No. ORQ-562 was adopted. The document was adopted by the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 17, 2019 and approved by the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 23, 2019. From the point of view of introducing gender equality, it is necessary to emphasize the positive changes in education. That is, since 2017, the activity of part-time departments in various specialties has been restored in most higher education institutions. This form of education gives young women the opportunity to pursue higher education while taking care of children and other family responsibilities.

In June 2019, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said in the Senate of the Oliy Majlis: "I am very concerned about the stereotype that has appeared in the minds of our people. Usually we respect a woman, first of all, as a mother, as a guardian of the family fortress. This is undoubtedly true. But today, every woman should be not just an observer, but also an active and proactive participant in the democratic changes taking place in the country." noted.

These transformation processes can be seen in the development trend of Western and Eastern civilizations, scientific, social, political and philosophical thinking. Now let's briefly touch on the views of Western and Eastern scholars and members of the Jadidist movement. Socrates was sentenced to death on the charge of poisoning the minds of young people with his ideas about personal freedom and liberty, human and civil rights. Plato, the father of philosophy, also supported these views in his work "The Ideal State", showing his loyalty to the ideas of his great comrades. Plato concludes that the difference between male and female nature is relative and applies only to the reproductive sphere. A woman can choose professions of her choice: music, philosophy or other professions, including military work. In Plato's work, "Can a woman be considered capable of performing this difficult and responsible task? Can the female part of humanity participate in all matters along with men?" , raises questions. Plato reveals the social roots of the problem by describing this truth about the

place of women in society, who were condemned to "cooking soup" and "babysitting" as a result of the strong and long-term influence of traditions and customs. The Roman statesman and jurist Emilius Papinian writes about the position of women in society: "According to the general rules of our law, the position of women is worse than that of men." Although a woman was free, she did not have civil rights. For example, he could not serve in the army, vote in assemblies, be elected to public office, be a judge or prosecutor, or be a third-party lawyer.

In the East, a woman has always been glorified as a man's friend, friend, intelligent, kind, and leader of family peace. In the Eastern thought, in the Turkic peoples, the status of women in society was very high. Arab historian Ibn Battuta informs: "When Turkish khagans signed, they wrote "by order of the sultan and his wife". Islam ranks men who treat their women well among the best of people. In this regard, it is said in the hadith: "The best among you is the one who behaves well towards the women of his people" (narration of Imam Tirmidhi). Islam rejected the traditions of Jahiliyyah, protected women and elevated them to higher levels. Prophet Muhammad (pbuh): "O people! Respect the rights of women. Treat them with compassion and love. Fear God regarding their rights! Wives are God's trust for you. You promised them in the name of God, and they became lawful to you by divine command. Just as you have rights over your wives, so do women have rights over you. Your rights over wives are that they do not trample on the honor of the family to anyone you do not like.

In his pedagogical views, Abdulla Avloni mentions that the peace of the family is directly in the hands of smart, intelligent, insightful, well-educated women. In his work, Adib quotes parents' advice to girls starting a family and emphasizes that peace and happiness in the family is the responsibility of more women: "O my daughter! You are leaving the home you have learned to marry and entering an unfamiliar house. You do not know all the qualities of your future husband. Be earth, and he will be heaven. If you are humble before him like earth, he will be heaven." As the sky blesses the earth with its healing rain, let your husband hear only soft and sweet words from you.

Abdurauf Fitrat's views on the issues of family relations are also noteworthy. In a number of his works, there are opinions that women should be well-mannered, educated, faithful, shy, shy, brave, deeply in love with their husbands, thinking about giving birth and raising children, not oppressing, obedient to their husbands, polite, correct, modest and prudent, well aware of their duties and responsibilities, and thrifty.

Here, Alisher Navoi, a thinker of the Turkic language, in the chapter "On Marriage and Wives" of the work "Mahbub ul-Qulub" expresses thoughts about marriage and its benefits, family etiquette and the virtues of women in the family: "A good wife is the state and happiness of the family. The house is tidy from her, the owner of the house is calm and peaceful from her. "If you are polite, you will be happy. If you are wise, there will be order in the household, and the equipment will be clean and organized."

In the era of modernizing Uzbekistan, unique Eastern means, forms and methods of gender equality are widely used. As a result of ensuring gender equality between women and men, it is possible to recognize that household chores, raising children and all other tasks are assigned not to women, but also to fathers. It is also worth noting that it can be said that parents paying attention to the issues of Western gender equality and Eastern gender equality from the point of view of mentality will serve to further clarify the issue..

References:

1. Article 46 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: "Uzbekistan", 1992.
2. Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech at the twentieth plenary session of the Oliy Majlis Senate on June 21, 2019.
3. Plato. Dialogue [Dialogues]. Translation from ancient Greek. Khar'kov, Folio Publ., 1999. - 383 p.
4. Gurevich D., Rapsat-Sharle M. -T. Povsednevnyaya jizn ginseng in Ancient Rome. - Moscow, 2006. - S. 239–240.
5. Alisher Navoi. "Mahbub ul-Qulub" (Proverbs and stories dear to hearts). Translated into the current Uzbek language. - Tashkent: "Sano-standard", 2018.

